

DIFFERENCES AMONG THE USA PRESIDENTS IN HOW THEY APPROACHED THE CONDUCT OF FOREIGN POLICY AND THE ISSUE OF NATIONAL INTEREST.

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Annotation: The following article is focused to show some of the differences among the Presidents of the USA, especially, Nixon, Carter, Reagan, Bush I, Clinton, and Bush II. Therefore, insight into the issue of national interest is raised and weaved through each of the Presidents and their time in office.

Keywords: Foreign policy, discrediting, anti-crisis regulation, threat impeachment, socio-economic policies, free market economy.

Today, America and its method of government are considered by many politicians to be the main topic of discussion (after Ukraine and Russia, of course). Basically, they are divided into two fronts: those who support the foreign policy of President Biden and those who are against it. But let's look at this problem from the root, that is, from the beginning. In this essay, I will look at the methods of introducing the political affairs of Nixon, Reagan, Carter, Bush I, Bush II, and Clinton. In addition, I will try to look at their political interests during their administration.

According to the book Kristen J. Dolan, "A Comparative Analysis of American Foreign Policy Toward the Middle East" [1], Richard Nixon's journey to the White House was long and arduous, yet it was also replete with opportunities to gain valuable foreign policy experience.

Furthermore, in Master of Arts in Political Science, professor J. Dolan from the University of Nevada, did some research. According to it, Carter's perception of American foreign policy during the Nixon-Ford years was that it had been allowed to become too narrowly defined in terms of the Soviet-American competition in the Cold War.

In addition, a journalist from California University Lou Cannon [2] analyzes Reagan's domestic and foreign affairs and wrote an article. As written in the article Reagan's policies were abysmal. His "trickle-down" economics was a total failure that has burdened America with trillions in debt and a corrosive mindset that is still strong today.

The book "Reconstructing Consensus American Foreign Policy since the Vietnam War" written by Richard A. Melanson [3] also explains the political state during Bush Jr. "Bush's presidency, viewed through the lens of public opinion, can be evaluated as a success, with an overall job approval rating better than all but two presidents since World War II" he writes in his book.

For Nixon, foreign policy was important. When he was preparing to enter the political arena again, foreign issues served as his talking point. He aspired to build a name for himself in foreign affairs. And Nixon realized that the world was a chessboard, unlike many other leaders. This prompted him to micromanage the game, which led him to make several clumsy interventions:

- Sidelining the State Department (and his hapless legal colleague Rogers), because he demanded to run foreign affairs out of the White House; at least he found a Kissinger.
- Meddling in the SALT missile treaty negotiations, and sidelining the professional negotiators in place, which meant that the US ended up with a bad deal.
- Unnecessary cloak and dagger theatricality around negotiating the overture to China.
- Counterproductive reliance on personal relationships; a big reason why he gave Pakistan a pass was that he personally disliked Indira Gandhi, while Zia of Pakistan was his trusted intermediary to China.
- A lot of over the top, Madman Theory theatrics in his prosecution of the Vietnam War, that did not end up working, and that cost a lot of lives to little effect.
- Counterproductively hard-hatted foreign policy, that certainly backfired in Chile and Cambodia.

Nixon being Nixon about foreign policy, with all the personality defects that came with it, means that he didn't achieve as much lasting difference as he'd hoped or thought he'd achieved.

It seems to me that some of what I would call successes were considered failures by many Americans. I believe others will list some of Carter's achievements and I will refrain from giving an exhaustive list and focus on something that is usually hidden to view by the press and the cunning US politicians. For me, Carter's negotiations with Israel and Egypt showed that, unlike many presidents who came after him, Carter did not show as much favoritism for Israel. He managed to induce Israel to back out of the Sinai and for that, he needs to be thanked. In return, he made some concessions to Israel but he did not pamper them the way, for example, Trump does, "giving" them more Palestinian and Arab land, which only serves to polarize the Middle East more, creating dangerous conflict.

Ronald Wilson Reagan was a president who brought about change. He helped pave the way for a peaceful end to the Cold War through his leadership and the symbiotic relationship he developed with Soviet leader Mikhail Gorbachev during their four summit talks. Reagan's supporters said that he had "won" the Cold War as the Soviet Union vanished into the mists of time. Prudently, Reagan and Gorbachev declared that everyone was a winner. Reagan had a good reason to feel that the West had won the ideological conflict, though; in his words, democracy had triumphed in its protracted "war of values" with collectivism.

With an overall job approval rate better than all but two presidents since World War II, Bush's presidency can be judged success from the perspective of public opinion. Bush was also a president whose performance assessments improved significantly in just four years. His first three years in government had strong ratings due to historic foreign initiatives and events, but his support subsequently declined in his re-election year due to a deteriorating economy and ineffective domestic policies.

In the process of reading this book, I realized that a crucial idea in international relations is "national interest." Every country is constantly working to achieve or secure the objectives of its national interests. Each country's foreign policy is developed based on its own national interests and is always working to achieve its objectives. Each state has the unalienable right to

protect its own national interests. A state always tries to use its national interest as a justification for its actions. A state's actions are always influenced and controlled by its own national interests. Therefore, understanding the definition and scope of national interest is crucial for us. The book, helped me understand the worldviews and ways of thinking of presidents in power at different times. Critically, the flaw in the book is that it only tells us about one side of the coin. I mean, it would have been nice if the author had included the failures and wrong decisions of the presidents. This would have given the reader a more accurate picture of what was going on at the time.

References:

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